

Employees Retention in Tanzania Public Educational Institutions: Educational Business Study Case of Tanzania Public Service College (TPSC)

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Abstract:- This education case study was done at Tanzania Public Service College (TPSC) Dar es Salaam, whereby 70 respondents participated. The general case objective was to investigate the employees' retention scenario at the College. Specific objectives were to: Identify techniques/methods employed by TPSC management to retain employees at work, analyze problems which TPSC faced on course of retaining employees and assess the extent to which TPSC management strived to solve problems they faced. Findings indicated that techniques/methods used to retaining employees included: The use of weekly and monthly meetings between TPSC management and employees, provision of training opportunities both short and long time training to employees, timely salary restructuring and effective and timely payments of honoraria and other payments dues, securing of loans from finance institutions and employee binding contract when securing loans and before attending long courses, as well. It is concluded that TPSC succeeded to increase the rate of retention of employees and that frequent innovations .of techniques/methods facilitated the effectiveness of the methods/techniques. It is recommended that the number of techniques to be increased and similar study to be done at other similar organizations to enable different researchers to come with the converging conclusion and recommendations.

Keywords:- Employee Retention, Training Opportunities and Management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tanzania Public Service College being public education agency came into operation on 31st January, 2020 after its Establishment Order being published through the Government Gazette (G.N. 64). The aim of the Agency is to enhance the public service capacity, systems, skills and culture for continuous improved public service performance and delivery. This merger came as a result of the studies done by different stakeholders for the purpose of improving Tanzania public Service provision quality. TPSC was tasked to increase the enrollment of students by opening a number of branches across the country and that resulted also into the increase of number of employed staff both support and academic staff.

With regard to enhancement of systems, TPSC is tasked with improvements and efficiencies as well as effective operations of available systems. The Human Resources Management System among other duties undertakes recruitment of new staff. The recruitment is open and that it follows the government rules, regulations and procedures. The central government through its ministry/agency harmonizes all recruitment procedures. The Human Resources Management System undertakes all staff matters which include day to day management, staff promotion, retirement and training as well incentive provision. The training policy stipulates in-service training which includes short and long courses, seminars and workshops. The provision of training to a particular staff is based on the identification of training and assessment needs. The effective implementation of the planned training budget for staff depends on the available fund which originates from the central government.

It is also purported that staff training entails the staff gaining competencies for particular occupations in TPSC or any other public institutions undertaking similar operations. The competence gained by the staff is of two fold; Knowledge and skills. In this case, gained knowledge is usually integrated into practice a situation which is explained to result into 'skill'. It is therefore commended that TPSC graduates are expected to demonstrate competencies gained from TPSC into public services. The competencies are expected to be demonstrated through undertaking different operations/tasks in their area of specializations (occupations). For example, records management, customer care services, secretarial services just to mention a few being an occupations, one is expected to demonstrate her/his competencies by providing quality service delivery based on knowledge gained from the College.

The Human Resources, Accounting and Computerized Systems also ensure effective utilization of TPSC physical resources and the all procurement and supply issues. The health and safety system is set to ensure health of employees and the safe use of facilities/equipment at work place. The system is harmonized by the health and safety policy. According to the policy, every TPSC member of staff shall be a member of National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) and must contribute to the NHIF from his/her monthly salary. The implementation of the policy is explained to result into

motivation of staff and their families because they are sure of getting immediate medical treatments upon being sick.

Furthermore, TPSC capitalizes on teaching cultural transformation to ensure good public performance. Students are charged with the task of learning our culture from the early ages to gain knowledge and skills for good practice. Aisley (2019) explains that every institution have its own culture and that there is inter related cultural relationship between institutions. According to Koinange (2016) many issues influencing the performance of institutions are influenced by the institution culture. In this regard, it the same culture which is projected to practiced by TPSC graduate in all public sectors. However, it is explained that the cultural practices in public sectors is greatly influenced by both internal and external issues which this case study intends to unfold.

II. BACKGROUND TO THE CASE AND CASE OBJECTIVES

A. Tanzania Public Service College Overview

The year 2022 marks 22 years of Tanzania Public Service College, the public college that provides short courses training in Leadership and Management is one amongst the leading Colleges in Tanzania in providing knowledge and skills required for good performance in public sectors. The core values of TPSC revolve around customer focus, impartiality, innovation, patriotism and professionalism. These values describe the culture of the TPSC in its service delivery to ensure internal and external customers of the College experience high satisfaction as harmonized by TPSC objectives, mission and vision.

The objectives of its establishment was to fill an extant void in terms of a comprehensive training facility for Public Service, to meet the changing needs of Public Services resulted from the Public Service Reform, and the need for an autonomous financially sustainable public service College.

These objectives are underpinned by the mission which is “To build the public and private sector capacity and competencies through comprehensive training, applied research, consultancy and technology based sharing platforms for delivery of quality services.” and the vision which is To be a center of excellence in facilitating knowledge sharing for quality public service delivery” It is anticipated that synchronization of TPSC objectives, mission and vision aim at enabling the college to be among the best colleges in producing competent graduates to work in public sections.

With the capacity of 15000 students, the number of employees is 256 which mark the deficiency of 100 employees. The denomination with regard to the number of employees is the academic staff is (59%) and support staff is (41%). This is in line with the response from TPSC Executive Director that the college is faced with lack of enough academic and support staff. He continued to highlight that *‘lack of enough staff automatically affects the*

performance of the institution and employees the latter are overloaded’.

The academic staff for example, finds difficulties to practice their competencies in big classes as well as delivering in within many hours during teaching. The TPSC workload policy stipulates the workload for every lecturer in-terms of hours per week and that for extra hours payments must be effected as honoraria. The TPSC (2021) report indicates the colleges spent TZS 1,347,846,069 as compensation for extra hours beyond normal. Spending this huge amount of fund gives an indication of lack of permanent academic staff. This lead to the challenge of big workload and management spent substantial amount for extra hour as teaching allowances instead of improving other staff incentives that would have motivated staff to stay, hence staff retention difficulties.

TPSC sources of funds are primarily fees payable by students, and all collected funds are retained by the College and spent as per approved annual budget of the College. Therefore, the College have prepare annual budget indicating the amount needed for each Directorate/Campus/ Unit settings. The TPSC reports (2020- 2022) indicates that because of the Competitiveness in the industry students enrollments have been constantly declining at the average rate of 9,9% which in turn has caused declining of the College’s collections. This is explained to have negative impact on the budget to furnish for employee benefits and sequentially employee retention becomes difficulty each year. According to the reports, negative impact is on the recruitments of new staff, annual leave payments, staff training, procurement of physical facilities (particularly for lectures’/students’ training/learning facilities). It is explained that lack of funds have been resulting into failure to recruit people according to TPSC’s manning level. In light to this, there are number of staff who was not allowed to pursue further studies due to shortage of fund to finance their studies, as well as failure to procure enough training/learning facilities and equipment. Furthermore, fewer funds collected by College affects the renovations of old buildings as well as erecting new buildings.

Failure to renovate buildings, the outcome is the abandonment of the buildings for use. Similarly, failure to erect new building, in line with the increase in number of students and human resources results into lack of enough buildings for the effective implementation of TPSC core values. In a nut shell, all of these are issues which impinge on human resources management. Since each human being is unique, it is anticipated that employees faced with these issues may decide to remain in employment or quit from TPSC employment.

The fewer funds contrary to actual amount stipulated in the budget have been a constraint to the Finance and Accounts department. The department has to struggle through-out the year to do re-allocation of funds from one vote to another to ensure smooth and proper flow of funds. In this case, due to human error and uniqueness the re-allocation of funds may result into other department

embarrassments and hence, de-motivation of employees in the respective section/departments. It is also anticipated that effective re-allocation of funds needs competent and qualified accountant. According to TPSC (2022), the department of Finance and accounts has only 35% of qualified accountant. This is a challenge to member of staff in the department who lacks required qualifications. In this regard, lacking such qualifications has been indulging into 'work crises' is also among issues influencing employee retention.

The TPSC's vision is to be the best leading professional institution in Tanzania by providing training to trainees needed for good performance in public sectors. However, the stipulated issues have been putting in place the performance of TPSC questionable. In spite of all issues which TPSC has been faced, is considered as one of the best professional college in Tanzania and has been taken by National Council for Technical Education (NACTE) as a college model. Therefore, to overcome issues which have been impinging challenges to staff retentions/performance as well as management challenges, TPSC have been in inter-relationship with other experienced colleges and universities inside and outside the country for better understanding on how to manage issues which influence staff retention and hence, improve the performance of College. However, techniques on how to solve stipulated issues including staff retention in line with factors contributing to retention, implementation of policies on recruitment, motivation and remunerations, training and wage payment, which may be appropriate to be precise to dissect the problem. The following are techniques which the TPSC have employed.

B. Management Techniques

TPSC management believe that good management and transparency on dissemination of information are sole parameters for solving all managerial problems including employees' retention. Adhering on chain of command among employees in different levels of management was observed to a great extent solve a number of complains among employees. This was facilitated by the existence of stable organization structure into which every manager/section leader have clear and defined scope of boundary with regard to management power and dissemination.

The existence of well stipulated human resource policy which is effected through rules and regulations whereby clear steps/procedures for dealing with complains are stipulated. In light of these, the availability of complains desk as well as the suggestion box are explained to motivate employees to perceive TPSC community as part and parcel of their lives and hence, the love to stay. The TPSC (2021) a number of rewards the management provided employees for performing better in different work perspectives. The rewards types ranged from monetary to non-monetary rewards, according to the report, the availability of reward management system entailed effective of rewards provision which reduced the rate of favouritism and victimization. Training of employees being among types of rewards available was explained to be properly managed and training

was provided to employees based on individual training needs as well as TPSC needs.

Sharing of information regarding the institution performance, provided the employees chance to share their ideas concerning a concerning issues at work, task to complete with their own pace was the ideal of TPSC. All narrated above were TPSC management techniques to manage prevailed issue on course of facilitating the retention of employees. It is also anticipated that the employed management technique improves the retention because employees felt part of the TPSC which institution, appreciated, motivated and enhanced their performances. Through this practice, the strong institution culture of TPSC was created, as employees need to be innovative and TPSC needs to adopt idea brought by employees as well.

C. Improving Payment System

TPSC effected innovations in the department of finance by introducing first in first out mode of paying employees their dues as well as incentives. The innovation was associated with the management efforts to increase projects which resulted into the increase of funds from income generating projects. 60% of funds generated from short course project were used to pay tutors and other direct expenses incurred in the course of running the course and the remaining part (40%) were used for other College activities. This supplemented funds from central government which also was used for training of employees in and outside the country as well as improving employee incentives.

It was contended that innovations with regard to the payments system provided conducive work environment and that employees were motivated to work with TPSC. In light of this, there was transparency in all payments which reduced complains among employees and this resulted team work in the entire TPSC community. To a great extent the innovation facilitated so much in getting work done on time and effectively and enhanced personal career performance of an employee. Thus, this motivated employees and according to Pasad (2007) this is among techniques of employees' retention.

D. Investigating Causes of Existing Problem in TPSC

The best way of dealing with existing problem in any institution is by knowing the causes of that problem. In this regard, TPSC management have to embark on employing different investigation methods and instruments such as interviews and that the researcher on the issues concerning retention of employees should be researched. The researcher prepared interview questions (instrument) for the purpose of unfolding issues catalysing employee's retention at TPSC. In light of this, the employees who exited from TPSC may also be interviewed. Vital data was collected which was paramount important for issues influencing the retention of employees in this educational institution.

E. Training and Development

TPSC core activities include teaching, doing research and consultancy. These tasks need competent personnel in terms of knowledge and skills in respective field of specialization. In different courses offered by TPSC to students, there is a great need of professionalism and that plans for training of trainers as well as developing them of equal important.

Despite the fact that there is a good training and development plan for employees, the issue is availability of enough funds. The researcher therefore may critically investigate the issue for the purpose of proposing techniques to be employed to solve the problem. This will be opportunity for proposing techniques for the growth of their carrier while continuing working.

F. Formulating Employees Succession Plan

It is contended that for any formal or informal organization to sustain and survive there is a need to have succession plan which transparently shows type/category of like this, some employees would feel safe and certain about the future. According to TPSC, it was not about retaining employees only, but also thinking of their future careers and wishes as well.

It is anticipated that all employees may like to gain power by climbing up in the organization hierarchy. This entails the availability of the mechanism to make them grow within the TPSC and hence attain good position.

G. Develop Policy and Organization System

With growth of employee everything may become completed and employee needed to be conceded good to other, employees would have a misconceptions with regard to their work titles and managerial positions and some might be resistant to management and thus at this stage, it was mandatory to TPSC to have written code of professional conduct on how to behave, how to lodge complain if someone mistreated and how salary/incentives is being paid. All these together are TPSC policy and structure and these facilitate easiness to manage the TPSC and all employees are joyful with safe employment.

The above are the techniques employed by TPSC to retain employees in employment. It should be conceived that issues influenced retention of employees were not fully TPSC exhausted by TPSC. However, the management is still striving to ensure employee retention, Therefore, the main objective of this case is to unfold the techniques the TPSC is employing to halt issues influencing retention of employees and as a researcher cum part of TPSC management thereafter to make precise and critical conclusion as well as putting forward recommendations for immediate actions as well as further research on similar cases.

It is from the above perspectives, the general case study objective was to investigate the employees' retention scenario at the college and specifically to case identified techniques/methods employed by TPSC management to retain employees at work, analyzed problems which TPSC faced when using those techniques/methods and assess the extent TPSC management strived to solve problems they faced.

III. CASE PROBLEM AND LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Case Problem

TPSC since establishment has been striving to develop the raising issues which are affecting retention of employees. The institution being public education organization and tasked to provide training to public employees as well as the like needs both academic and non academic employees for effective implementation of her core and non core business. However, the employees' retention issues necessitated the institution to hire part time lecturers and non academic staff to bridge the academic and administrative staff gaps by reducing big workload which was carried by permanent staff in both academic and administration sections. It is a fact that TPSC was informed on the issues influencing the retention of employees which included institution timely wage payments. While employees are expected to be highly and fairly paid/compensated for the time and effort they had put in the office; wages would show how the employer valued the time and work the employee had put in the office.

Another issue which led to employee retention in TPSC is said to be proper training and development which resulted for employees to get opportunity to enhance their competencies. This positively improved their effort to develop and overcome challenges to develop in their respective professional carrier. Dowmans (2015) asserts that for the purpose of balancing the politics at workplace the institution must be eager to equally enhance competences of all employees. According to Dowmans (ibid), employees need to develop by getting knowledge, skills and having enough finance. His observation is valid due to the fact that completion of training results into employee promotion and hence, salary increase. Failure to abide on human resources policies is another anticipated employees' issue which has been influencing employees' retention issues.

In some cases, it is reported exist favouritism with regard to provision of rewards to employees and despite clear policy stipulation on the jargon of 'First in First Out'.

This in fact may critically results into disembarking of frustrated employees from the job for the purpose of having safe work environments which is free from fear and victimization. In this regard, employees may be motivated to work in institutions which managers who implement human resource policy.

B. Literature Review

➤ *Employee Retention in Brief Context*

Employee retention is a much-studied phenomenon. There is a vast literature on the causes of voluntary employee retention dating back to the 1960s. A number of researches are based on only a small number of variables which often only explain a small amount of variability in employees retention. Another explanation on employee retention studies is that they do not adequately capture the complex psychological processes involved in individual retention decisions.

However, there have been a number of issues that are paramount and consistently and in line to employee retention. Kaijaly (2020) (1979) contends that age, tenure, overall satisfaction, job content, intentions to remain on the job, and commitment were all negatively related to turnover (i.e. the higher the variable, the lower the turnover). In 1995, a meta-analysis of some 800 turnover studies was conducted by Hom and Griffeth, which was recently updated (Griffeth et al, 2000). Their analysis confirmed some well-established findings on the causes of turnover. These include: job satisfaction, organizational commitment, comparison of alternatives and intention to quit. These variables are examined in more detail below, as are a number of other factors where the evidence on the link to turnover is less conclusive.

The relationship between alternatives and retention on an individual level has been researched widely since Dorican (2012) seminal work on ease of movement. Much of the subsequent research focused on the link between job satisfaction, perceived alternative opportunities and turnover. Later, researchers began to focus on the role of both actual and perceived opportunities in explaining individual turnover decisions. Subsequent study has indicated that actual alternatives are a better predictor of individual turnover than perceived opportunities. Research on the impact of unemployment rates as a proxy for actual opportunities in employee turnover revealed that unemployment rates affected the job-satisfaction/turnover intent relationship but not actual turnover (Gosleg, 2011). They concluded that macro level analysis predicted retention categories but perceptions of opportunities did not. This point was reinforced in their study on medical centres in various locations used measures of perceived and objective opportunities in internal and external labour markets. The researchers concluded that objectives opportunities were a better set of explanations of actual turnover behavior than either perceived internal or external labour market opportunities.

Dragon (2008) on employee relations, emphasized about key motives behind employees to gain employment, where the motive is money and career opportunities, the expectation is always met but retention is still a great issue. The performance of TPSC tend to be disappointed by a lack of effective interactions with and appreciation from the institutions, long working hours and poor work life balance as well as lack of interesting work and lack of international

secondment. Thus, it is not only about money that will keep an employee other factors have to be considered.

➤ *Employee and Employee Retention*

Although the word "employee retention" has many different definitions, it generally refers to the various steps taken by firms to motivate their staff members to stay with the company for a longer period of time. To keep its talented personnel from departing is the main justification for employee retention (James and Mathew, 2012). Matthias Zeuch (2016), discusses about engagement and retention on the issues of employee and labour relation, reward and recognition, management ideas, retention tools and culture and social activities. The author emphasises more on how companies should develop an in-depth awareness of their employee's needs, by conducting a survey of employees so that they can be able to develop measures that are matching their needs. As well as researching on the issues of employee's exhaustion and dedication because their different from one another. Gonzalez Roma et al (2006) argue that the job engagement is associated with sustainable workload, feeling of choice and control, appropriate recognition and reward, a supportive work community, fairness and justice and meaningful and valued work.

Retention is the practice of motivating personnel to stay for a long time or until the project is completed, according to Hom and Griffeth (1995). According to Wysocki, (1997), employee retention is the trendiest concern right now. There are numerous reasons for an individual to voluntarily leave their job, according to Terence et al. (2001). Some may be impacted by organizational issues, while others may be personal. personal factors, including the state of the family, professional advancement, and alluring employment offers, etc. Lack of promotion chances, unjust employee treatment, and a mismatch between personal and organizational values are some organizational factors. Turnover in general is a major issue for both organization and individual. In light of this, it is made very apparent that experiencing shock, whether expected or unexpected, triggers strong feelings (i.e., an intention to flee). Positive, negative, or neutral shocks can all occur. Positive examples include different job offers, pregnancy to mention a few. Negative examples include friends departing and poor performance reviews to mention a few. Neutral examples include a spouse moving, administrative changes to mention a few.

IV. THE CASE METHODOLOGY

The case study was done at TPSC and respondents were 70 who were randomly and purposively sampled. Random sampling was first employed and this enabled the researcher in this case study to get participants with desirable prior stated characters. Since the number of participant from random sampling method was big compared to the required, purposive sampling method was then funnily used to get the exact number of participants.

TPSC was studied because apart from being giant education training institution in the country, it has been experiencing issues concerning both retention and labour turnover. Case study research design was used and both primary and secondary data was collected through the use data collection methods such as interviews, observations and documentary review. In this case, both open and closed ended interview questions were used during interviews. The researcher collected responses on the issues concerning employee’s retention as well as the suggestions for combating issues. The observation schedule was used to observe incidences in work environments: specifically on work tools/equipment, training settings and the like. Documentary review and documentary review schedule enabled the researcher to collect quantitative data from documents. Analysis of data was done based on research objectives.

V. CASE FINDINGS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

A. Management Techniques/Methods Employed to Effect Employees’ Retention

It was revealed from the case study that 14(20%) of employees mentioned that week and every end of the month meetings were done where by both employees and employers met to discuss major issues which emerged within the week/month and the solution for the purpose of moving forward have been jointly discussed. Respondents 3(4.3%) from this group explained that such meetings enabled them to address their problems to the employers.

They continued to explain that the act of addressing our grievances concerning work to employer enabled the employer to understand what they needed to get from them. On this case, one respondent narrated further that ‘..... I requested my employer during the meeting that my immediate supervisor was harassing me and that I was on course of quitting from the job’. The respondent explained further that immediately during the meeting the supervisor was told to stop harassing her and the latter stopped the plan to quit from the job. It was also revealed from the study that

during the meeting both employer and employees through discussion reached a stage of planning on how to benefit and share the profit TPSC obtained from income generation projects. According to all respondents, the college generated profits and through the meeting the consensus was reached that every employee should enjoy the profit gained from income generating projects.

The review of documents through the use of documentary review method the researcher discovered that 35(50%) of the profit was decided to distributed equally to each employer. Review of documents revealed further that for the period of 2015 to 2020 each employer was given Tshs. 120,000 as part of share from generated profits from income generation projects. The period of 2001 to 2012, each employer was given Tshs. 180,000 from the profit obtained from income generation projects. Respondents 42(60%) explained that the profit was a motivation that encouraged them to remain working with TPSC in beliefs that every year they will be getting this share and continue to use them for social needs issues.

It was also revealed from the study that from the meeting conducted that were provided the assurance from the TPSC management that their work lives environment may be enriched from time to to the extent every employee will enjoy working with this institution. According to these findings, 15 employees voiced that such assurance from the employer encouraged them frequently and timely to attend the job and work hard. One respondent from this group praised this by narrating that ‘..... many employees including me we are happy we are feeling to be part and parcel of TPSC I will retire in this organization if god wishes’. The findings are in line with Dorican (2012) who commends that conducive work environment is among ingredients which influence retention of employees in various organizations.

The validation of the effective with regard to the use of meetings was done through the review of TPSC documents and findings are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Meeting Done at TPSC from 2017 to 2022

YEAR	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018
Weekly meeting	40(83.3%)	38(79.2%)	42(87.5%)	30(62.5%)	35(72.9%)
Meeting not done	8(12.7%)	10(20.8%)	6(12.3%)	5(37.5%)	13(27.1%)
Monthly meeting	9(75%)	10(83.3%)	11(91.7%)	6(50%)	11(91.6%)
Meeting not Done	3(25%)	2(16.6%)	1(8.3%)	6(50%)	1(8.3%)

Source: TPSC, 2023.

It was also revealed by 23(32.8%) respondents that provision of training to employees was another management technique used by TPSC to retain employees. Respondents explained that they have been attending different trainings which resulted into enrichment of their competencies interms of knowledge and skills. 10 respondents (14.2%) from academic group explained that the college provided them opportunities to attend short and long courses. Similarly, 6 respondents (8.6%) from a group of support staff narrated similar story that TPCS asked them to choose

courses which were beneficial to them and the college and after choosing them the college sponsored them. Analysis of this response indicates the hope contained in employees heart to continue working with TPSC till 2027 hopping to be provided training. Review of documents indicated for example, for the year 2020, 30% of employees were provided training and for the tear 2021, 50% of respondents were provided training.

Similarly for the year 2022, 61% of total employees were provided training. Further analysis on the validity of this technique revealed that for the year 2020, employees 10% attended long courses and 30%. Similarly for the year 2021, 10% of total employees attended long courses and 40% attended short courses. For the year 2022, 12% attended long courses and 49% attended short courses. It was revealed from the study for those who were offered long courses were supposed to sign the contract of 5 years of remain in TPSC employment and this was conceded by the researcher to enhance the retention of employees at TPSC. It was also revealed from the study that provision of rewards was another technique which TPSC management used as a technique to retain employees. According to 35 employees, the increase in remunerations motivated the employees love working with TPSC. They explained the recent improvement of salary structure resulted into a number of employees' salaries to rise.

Further analysis of this response revealed that apart from salaries, there were improvements with regard to honoraria and overtime payments. According to 6 respondents, the situation with regard to previous situation, such payments were not effectively paid despite the fact of being low. 3 respondents (4,3%) joyfully commended that they have been using honoraria and overtime payment for family matter and serving the salaries for future use. It was also revealed from the study that under this method (technique), TPSC management helped employees to secure loans which the repayments are done from the deductions

from employees' salaries. Review of documents revealed that in order to get loans from finance institutions, the employer and employees signed binding agreement with regard to the royalty of the latter to repay the loan from his/her salary deduction. The researcher conceded this binding agreement to be good for retaining the concerned employee.

B. Problems Faced TPSC Management on Course of Effecting Retention of Employees Techniques/Methods and the Extent TPSC have been Striving to Solve Them

According to 34(48.6%) respondents, sometimes these meetings were postponed to allow employees to accomplish various TPSC tasks. According to 12(17.1%) respondents, the period when lectures were invigilating examinations staff meeting had to be postponed and again that denied staff/employer rights to discuss matters concerning employers/employees and the issues pertaining the performance of TPSC.

It was revealed from the study that finance constraint have been labelled as causing problem to affect implementation of training and rewarding employees. According to 14(20%) respondents, TPSC have been getting no money from central government which eventually negatively affected the training budget. Review of documents revealed that for the past 5 years training budget have been decreasing harmonically as indicated in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Training Budget Rate -2017 to 2022

Year	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	2017
Budget rate (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100
Budget remitted (%)	83	70	45	72	80	69
Under budget (%)	17	30	55	27	20	31

Source: TPSC, 2022

It was revealed from the study that TPSC have been striving hard to cover the staff training budget gap. Three respondents (4.3%) mentioned that TPSC management have been establishing a number of income generation projects. Review of documents indicated that percentage from income generation projects which are managed by TPSC have been allocated for training as summarized in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Percentage of Money Injected int Training of Staff Budget from 2018 to 2022

Year	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018
% of money injected to Training of staff from incoming generation projects	20.1%	19%	13%	20%	5%

Source: TPSC, 2023

Data in Table 4.4 indicates that for the years 2018, 2019 and 2020, amount of money injected into staff training budget in-terms of budget was 5%, 20% and 13% respectively. Furthermore, for the years 2021 and 2022 amount of money TPSC allocated for training from income generation projects was 19% and 20.1% respectively. It was further revealed from the study that the amount of money from income generating projects was paramount important for boosting staff training budget and that to some extent stabilized the proposed staff training budget.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

It is hereby concluded that TPSC to a great extent succeed to retain employees in job through employment of various methods/techniques and that techniques employed are recommendable to other similar public organizations for their good performance. It is also concluded that the reported constant innovations with regard to the use of methods/techniques to retain employees in TPSC which have been showing improvements for employee retention rate as revealed in section four above.

B. Recommendations

Recommendations for immediate improvements to include: TPSC to continue making innovations to the existing method/techniques which have been in use to retain employees.

TPSC also to improve the quality of income generating projects observed not to perform well by the researcher for the purpose of improvement of the generated profit. TPSC management must always concretize employees on organization as well as the government financial un-stabilities which in most cases affect organizations' budget. It is recommended that further case study to be done in institutions undertaking similar functions so as to enable different researcher under similar study to come out with similar/different findings and conclusion.

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